

ATTRACTING TOURISTS WITH GASTRONOMY TOURISM TO UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11219060>

Abstract. *Gastronomy tourism is a type of travel that focuses on discovering the local ingredients, cuisine, and culinary customs of a place. Uzbekistan is one of the countries where food festivals and traditional food can attract tourists to the country. Gastronomic tourism can offer immersive cultural experiences and boost small businesses. The accessibility of food can assume a major part in finding an objective's picture. Food can show a remarkable encounter and joy to vacationers. The sightseer's fulfillment should be really significant on your rundown. There are various ways gastronomy and the travel industry can draw in sightseers to a particular country. One of the various ways is adding more customary dishes to your menu.*

Key words: *Gastronomy, Attract, Tourists, Festival, Traditional*

Annotatsiya. *Gastronomiya turizmi - bu joyning mahalliy ingredientlari, oshxonasi va oshpazlik odatlarini kashf etishga qaratilgan sayohat turi. O'zbekiston taom festivallari va an'anaviy taomlari sayyohlarni mamlakatga jalb qilishi mumkin bo'lgan mamlakatlardan biridir. Gastronomik turizm immersiv madaniy tajribalarni taklif qilishi va kichik biznesni rivojlantirishi mumkin. Oziq-ovqatning mavjudligi maqsadning rasmini topishda muhim rol o'ynashi mumkin. Taom dam oluvchilar uchun ajoyib uchrashuv va quvonchni ko'rsatishi mumkin. Ekskursantning bajarilishi sizning xulosangizda haqiqatan ham muhim bo'lishi kerak. Gastronomiya va sayyohlik sanoati ma'lum bir mamlakatga sayyohlarni jalb qilishning turli usullari mavjud. Turli usullardan biri bu sizning menyuingizga ko'proq odatiy taomlarni qo'shishdir.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Gastronomiya, Attract, Turistlar, Festival, An'anaviy*

Аннотация. *Гастрономический туризм — это вид путешествия, целью которого является знакомство с местными ингредиентами, кухней и кулинарными обычаями того или иного места. Узбекистан является одной из стран, где кулинарные фестивали и традиционные блюда могут привлечь туристов в страну. Гастрономический туризм может предложить захватывающий культурный опыт и стимулировать малый бизнес. Доступность еды может сыграть важную роль в определении цели. Еда может принести отдыхающим незабываемые впечатления и радость. Удовлетворенность экскурсанта должна иметь большое значение в вашем списке. Существуют различные способы, с помощью которых гастрономия и туристическая индустрия могут привлечь туристов в конкретную страну. Один из способов – добавить в меню больше традиционных блюд.*

Ключевые слова: *Гастрономия, Привлечение, Туристов, Фестиваль, Традиционный.*

INTRODUCTION

Food tourism, sometimes referred to as gastronomy tourism, has become incredibly popular in recent years. This unusual kind of travel centers on discovering the local, cuisine, culinary customs of a place and ingredients. It now plays a big role in drawing tourists and strengthening economies all around the world. The majority of people interested in traveling for gastronomic motivations started to increase gradually from the birth of 21st century (Krawiak &

Stasiak, 2015, as cited in Putra, 2021) Gastronomy tourism is becoming more and more popular for a number of reasons, including its capacity to offer deeply engaging cultural experiences, highlight regional uniqueness, and boost small businesses in the area. “Food can show an unforgettable experience and pleasure to tourists” (Kamrul, et al., 2020). The tourists' satisfaction is supposed to be the most important thing on your list. There are different ways gastronomy tourism can attract tourists to a specific country. One of the many different ways is adding more traditional dishes to your menu. Food also has become an essential part which is formed from plants, or animals to sustain human's biological needs. (Peres, 2021). Food tourism means enjoying new foods of destinations and exploring new culinary cultures and tastes. Food can be considered as both a product and a symbol through food related promotional activities such as food festivals and traditional food which can offer an evocative experience for tourists. How can we attract tourists to Uzbekistan with gastronomy tourism? Taking part in culinary excursions, making a dinner outing into an unforgettable experience as well as using regional ingredients to draw culinary visitors can be best ways to attract hordes of tourists to Uzbekistan.

Food Festivals and Outside Dining

Out of many different ways to attract tourists the initial ones to mention are food festivals and outside dining. The capacity of gastronomy tourism to offer immersive cultural experiences is one of the main reasons it appeals to tourists. “Food-related museums exhibiting tea culture and some annual food festivals are constructing a good atmosphere in culinary tourism in HongKong” (Sukenti.K, 2014) Like for example in Hong Kong they have food related museums and that can attract tourists to the country. We can create those types of events in Uzbekistan for tourists who are interested in food museums. People do not visit a country for only ancient touristic attractions but they also travel to try different dishes and food. We have to serve those tourists the way they enjoy and what they are mainly coming for. Adding extra activities can always be benefited by the country. According to Sukenti.K, “ Similar to Hong Kong, Singapore also has some annual event or festival in terms of cuisines which is effectively boosting their tourism visit”(2014). Events like festivals and cuisine demonstrations can boost up the tourists number in a major way because they like festivals and parties where there is different foods, desserts and even appetizers. With these kinds of events we can attract not only foreign guests but also may allure local tourists and residents of that region as well. Especially here in Uzbekistan people adore events like these, and the fact that if there is a party, with high probability anyone here will not miss this type of event. A place's history, customs, and social structure are strongly ingrained in its cuisine. Travelers can learn about a destination's culture and customs by sampling the local cuisine. Encountering local cuisine, going to food markets, taking cooking classes, and even learning about customary meal pairings all add to a whole cultural experience. Travelers can have a more genuine and satisfying experience by learning more about a place through gastronomy tourism than they might by just visiting its monuments and museums.

Traditional food can be so important for tourists especially for those who came specifically for the traditional dishes. Exploring regional diversity is another compelling feature of gastronomic tourism. “Almost all tourists, no matter the accommodation at which they are staying, provide food and beverages services or not, prefer to eat outside; and get to know and taste the local dishes belonging to the region.” (Tereshchuk, 2021). Every location has its own distinct cooking techniques, ingredients, and culinary customs. From rich pastries to fiery street food travelers can go on a culinary journey and experience the unique flavors of other places. This enables individuals to test their palates and widen their culinary horizons. According to

Tereshchuk “The travelers can be interested in the local food and in obtaining gastronomic experiences, and these experiences can even play an important role in the choice of the destination and in their level of satisfaction”. (2021). People who understand the traditional foods and dishes will definitely pick a country where they mostly serve the traditional foods. Gastronomy tourism encourages cultural exchange and the understanding and appreciation of diverse cuisines and cultures by embracing regional diversity.

The unique restaurants and cafes that can attract the tourists in quite different ways, Uzbekistan is one of country's with the best restaurants. People in Uzbekistan love guests and love love love restaurants. According to Tereshchuk, “in fact, there are already certain travelers who consider going to a specific restaurant or simply getting to know the cuisine of a specific geographic area better as the primary motivation for their trip.” (2021). Sometimes it is better to have a specific place in mind like Manaresa, Belis, Panorama, which are considered the best and most visited restaurants in Uzbekistan. Additionally, gastronomy tourism is essential to the growth of regional businesses. Travelers who partake in regional cuisine directly support the expansion of a destination's economy. The whole food supply chain, from neighborhood farmers and food producers to tiny, family-run eateries and street food vendors, gains from tourism. According to Sukenti, “tropical Garden Dining (dining in an excellent restaurant, located in a tropical garden), Waterfront Dining (dining in a restaurant near to canal, bay, river, lake, falls), Romantic dining, etc. This kind of categorization proves that Singapore is realizing its cuisine diversity and making some efforts to develop them seriously to be a unique item in their culinary tourism package.” (2014). When it comes to Uzbekistan, it is one of the best countries for dining restaurants near rivers, canals, lakes. The growing demand for regional foods supports numerous jobs in addition to aiding in the preservation of culinary traditions. Travelers who opt for culinary tourism can act as change agents by encouraging sustainable and ethical tourist activities.

Marketing Prospects for Culinary Tourism

The nations that have given that issue priority are developing the marketing prospects for culinary tourism. The desire of travelers to sample local cuisine in the locations and lodging establishments has set the stage in order to improve culinary tourism. Businesses in the tourism industry have incorporated gastronomic elements into their facilities after realizing the significance of gastronomy tourism as reported by both domestic and international visitors. Consequently, it is guaranteed that in order to give attention to gastronomy, tourism management should be coordinated with all foundations associated with tourism and civil society groups, as well as with the encouragement of pertinent ministries. In addition, gourmet tourism entrepreneurs must conduct promotional efforts in quantifiable methods. “The marketing opportunities to gastronomy tourism are being developed by the countries given importance to that issue” (Tereshchuk, 2021). Food tourism marketing campaigns use social media marketing, blogs, vlogs, and other promotional strategies to raise awareness of a tourist attraction. A destination will undoubtedly draw a large number of travelers from all over the world with food tourism. Us humans, we are always on social media! We look at things and we tend to go there or try what they show us on the web. Media is one of the most contiguous things in the present day. If we post our dishes, drinks and delicious looking food on our profiles we can get twice the visitors and people from all over the world.

Conclusions and Recommendations

In conclusion, gastronomy tourism is a powerful tool for attracting tourists and boosting local economies. Its ability to provide immersive cultural experiences, showcase regional

diversity, and support local businesses contribute to its growing popularity. As travelers seek more authentic and meaningful experiences, the appeal of exploring a destination's cuisine and culinary traditions is undeniable. With its potential to foster cultural exchange, gastronomy tourism is a win-win for both tourists and the local communities they visit. Gastronomy and the travel industry is perhaps the main justification for why individuals visit a particular country. Food has forever been the most awesome aspect of voyaging great, essentially for certain individuals. The accessibility of food can assume a major part in finding an objective's picture. Food can show a remarkable encounter and joy to vacationers. The sightseer's fulfillment should be really significant on your rundown. There are various ways gastronomy and the travel industry can draw in sightseers to a particular country. One of the various ways is adding more customary dishes to your menu.

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